

Enhanced Data Rate in nxDSL using DSLAM

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ABSTRACT

BSNL, the wireline incumbent operator in India, is experiencing negative growth in revenue from wireline sector and also unable to generate much revenue from highly competitive wireless sector services, has to hold its leadership in broadband service. The researcher has aimed to analyse the "Internal and Interactive Marketing Practices of BSNL in Promotion of Fixed Broadband Services". A strong theoretical support for the study was obtained by exploring the reviews from existing literatures, performance satisfaction, service quality, customer satisfaction, downloading, uploading and also studies related to the influence of socio, economic and demographic factors influencing broadband diffusion. The study identified that BSNL is required to be innovative and should focus more on their internal strategies. It is not only how the organization handles the service but also how it deals with its plan to promote its product and services. By doing so, it could not only retain its leadership position but also can create a tough competition for others in highly competitive broadband environment. The focus of this research is in the area of analyzing the performance of the new generation broadband networks like the Digital subscriber line (DSL), based on the parameters like noise margin, Attenuation and speed of internet. The research method adopted in this work includes designing of scenarios in the system level simulation tool C-DOT in BSNL Laboratory. These scenarios are simulated to study the effect of the customer site distances, speed and bandwidth on the network performance parameters. In this work, we propose a new technical architecture of broadband network system which suitable for nxDSL applications. Such can improve the Internet network performance high QoS and to enhance the transmission speed with low cost.

Keywords: Digital subscriber line, SNR, National Telecom Policy, POTS.

I. INTRODUCTION

In BSNL Annual Report 2012, it was stated that telecommunication which includes broadband has been recognized as a tool for development and also to overcome poverty [4]. Broadband, more than a network expansion of already existing networks like cable and telecommunication has also been recognized as a universal service. Finland declared broadband as universal service in 2010 (ITU NEWS, 2010). Due to wide value-added services in broadband, it is not a great task for newly entering operators or the private operators to promote it. But it is a tough task for the incumbent wireline operators to hold on their position and to become beneficiary out of it. DSL, network expansion of wireline infrastructure has undergone a tough competition from various operators within the sector and from other sectors in the last mile access.

Plain Old Telephone Service (POTS), or Plain Ordinary Telephone System, is a retronym for voice-grade telephone service employing analog signal transmission over copper loops. POTS was the standard service offering from telephone companies from 1876 until 1988 in the United States, when the Integrated Services Digital Network (ISDN) [5] Basic Rate Interface (BRI) was introduced, followed by cellular telephone systems, and voice over IP (VoIP).

1.1 Packet Aggregation

In Packet Aggregation a number of small packets are combined into larger packets. In this approach distributed aggregators are used to collect smaller packets through various network connections and assemble as a large packet [7,11]. In a packet-based communications network, packet aggregation is the process of joining multiple packets together into a single transmission unit, in order to reduce the overhead associated with each transmission [7,11]. The ITU-T G.hn standard [12], which provides a way to create a high-speed (up to 1 Gigabit/s) Local Area Network using existing home wiring (power lines, phone lines and coaxial cables), is an example of a protocol that employs packet aggregation to increase efficiency [6,7]. G.hn is a specification for home networking with data rates up to 2 Gbit/s and operation over four types of legacy wires: telephone wiring, coaxial cables, power lines and plastic optical fibre. A single G.hn [12] semiconductor device is able to network over any of the supported home wire

types. Some benefits of a multi-wire standard are lower equipment development costs and lower deployment costs for service providers (by allowing customer self-install) [7,11].

1.2 Packet Aggregation Network (PAN)

A system aggregates data packets communicated between one or more sessions on a source system and one or more sessions on a target system by: collecting one or more session packets from the one or more source system sessions; multiplexing the session data packets into an aggregated packet; sending the aggregated packet from the source system to the target system; and demultiplexing each aggregated packet into corresponding session packets for delivery to the sessions on the target system. An important design decision is the placement of (de)aggregation capabilities [7,11].

Fig-1: PAN Switch

The PAN Switch provides excellent port density for aggregation applications with 48 ports of 1G/10G and six ports of 40G. Features include any-to-any connectivity, aggregation, filtering, port tagging and trunking. In end-to-end aggregation the sender or ingress node aggregates the packets while the receiver or egress node de-aggregates the packets. Intermediate nodes just forward the aggregated packets [11]. Therefore, the aggregation is transparent to the backbone network and easy to deploy. On the other hand, valuable aggregation possibilities might be lost. In hop-by-hop aggregation every (back-haul) node de-aggregates and (re-)aggregates, which allows for efficient inter-flow aggregation. End-to-end packet aggregation has been shown to give a 120% improvement in capacity over an unaggregated case in a large-scale ad-hoc network [7].

Fig-2: Integration in a single IGP/LDP domain

The small-scale aggregation network is assumed to be composed of core & aggregation nodes that are integrated in a single IGP/LDP domain consisting of less than 1000 nodes [9]. LDP provides end to end reachability across the network. ALL mobile & wireline services are enabled by the aggregation nodes.

II. WORKING PRINCIPLE

2.1 Interior Gateway Protocol (IGP)

The Gateway Protocol is a type of protocol, used for exchanging routing information between gateways within an autonomous system. This routing information can then be used to route network layer protocol like IP [9].

2.2 Label Distribution Protocol (LDP)

The Distribution Protocol is a protocol in which router capable of multi-protocol label switching exchange label mapping information. The exchange of information is bi-directional [9].

2.3 MODEM

A MODEM is a hardware device that converts data into a format suitable for a transmitted from computer to computer. A MODEM modulates one and more carrier wave signals to encode digital information for transmission and demodulates signals to decode the transmitted information. A signal that can be transmitted easily & decoded to reproduce the original digital data. MODEM is generally classified by the max. amount of data they can send in a given unit of time, usually expressed in bits per second. Landline phones carry signals, broadband line also allow data from our internet service provider to be sent via DSL connection. DSL MODEM is the middle between our internet service provider & computer acting as a data translator that connect device to the internet. Dial-up internet which also uses a phone line, DSL allow to use phone while connected.

2.4 Optical Network Terminal (ONT)

An ONT is used to terminate the fibre optic line, demultiplex the signal into its component part (voice telephone, television & internet access) and provide power to customer telephone.

Fig-3: ONT configuration

2.5 Optical Line Terminal (OLT)

OLT also called optical line terminal, is a device which server as the service provider endpoint of a passive optical network.

Fig-4: OLT configuration

Digital subscriber lines such as ADSL, SHDSL and VDSL that operate over existing transmission lines are still on the top of telecommunication provider's interest [8]. Twisted copper pairs are a legacy cabling medium that deteriorates with time and can become a liability without proper maintenance. To avoid some of the high deployment costs of fibre, carriers will oftentimes build hybrid deployments using copper in the local subscriber loop and fibre in the remaining portion of a network. This form of deployment is known as FTTP (fibre to the premises) or FTTH (fibre to the home). Constant improvements in DSL equipment and chipsets in DSLAMs allow service providers to take advantage of the millions of copper telephone lines that have already been deployed. New chipsets such as G.Fast have been able to achieve up to 1 Gbps at its origin. Improvements such as this will continue to prolong the lifespan of copper pairs [13].

III. LITERATURE

K. R. Narayanan et al. [1] has said that, the India followed the mixed economy framework by combining the advantages of the capitalist economic system with those of the socialist economic system. Some scholars argue that, over the years, this policy resulted in the establishment of a variety of rules and laws, which were aimed at controlling and regulating the economy [1]. Globalisation is, thus, often seen as creating conditions for the free movement of goods and services from foreign countries that adversely affect the local industries and employment opportunities in developing countries. Leila Amdah et al. [2] has given the brief review about the Business process modelling. A DSL, meanwhile, allows a concise representation of the semantics of a particular business field, which allows the development of coherent and expressive business process models. Thus, these models can be use not only for modelling a system but also for generating executable applications. Collaborative business processes are increasingly present in practice. Their modelling, integration or execution becomes more and more complex because it involves an exchange of resources and data between several partners [1]. This paper presents a generic framework for process modelling language. Kiswanton et al. [3] has introduced and applied measurements with 30 MHz – 1 GHz range frequency. Faster wireless telecommunication systems are going to be the future of Telecommunication Industry. EMC issues and natural challenges arise with its growing entry in modern customer premises equipment (CPE). Further investigation about the electrical component of the ONT not investigated yet. The emission data of six different side from ONT has been presented using contour pattern measuring method. The method was used to analyses the radiation pattern of Optical Network Terminal (ONT) before and after treatment.

IV. PROPOSED WORK

SDSL support symmetric (downstream & upstream) data transmission up to 1-54Mbps. VDSL is the fastest of all XDSL flavours & provides transmission rate of 13-52Mbps downstream & 1.5-2.3Mbps upstream over a single copper wire at a distance of 1,000-4,500 feet from the service provider. ADSL support a range of asymmetric (down & up stream) data speed that can reach up to 7Mbps downstream & 1.5Mbps upstream. ADSL can deliver simultaneous high-speed data & telephone service over the same line. Modem initialization procedures are clarified, which improves interoperability and provides better performance when connecting ADSL transceivers from different chip suppliers. A fast start-up mode reduces initialization time from about 10 seconds to less than 3 seconds. Asymmetric Digital Subscriber Line (ADSL) is a type of Digital Subscriber Line (DSL) technology, a data communications technology that enables faster data transmission over copper telephone lines than a conventional voiceband MODEM can provide [10]. ADSL differs from the less common Symmetric Digital Subscriber Line (SDSL). In ADSL, bandwidth and bit rate are said to be asymmetric, meaning greater toward the customer premises (downstream) than the reverse (upstream). Providers usually market ADSL as an Internet access service primarily for downloading content from the Internet, but not for serving content accessed by others [5].

ADSL works by using spectrum above the band used by voice telephone calls. With a DSL filter, often called Splitter, the frequency bands are isolated, permitting a single telephone line to be used for both ADSL service and telephone calls at the same time. ADSL is generally only installed for short distances from the telephone exchange (the last mile), typically less than 4 kilometers (2 mi), but has been known to exceed 8 kilometers (5 mi); if the originally laid wire gauge allows for further distribution. At the telephone exchange, the line generally terminates at a Digital Subscriber Line Access Multiplexer (DSLAM) where another frequency Splitter separates the voice band

signal for the conventional phone network. Data carried by the ADSL are typically routed over the telephone company's data network and eventually reach a conventional Internet Protocol network [5]. When a connection is established between BNG and Customer Premise Equipment (CPE), the subscriber can access the broadband services provided by the Network Service Provide (NSP) or Internet Service Provider (ISP). BNG establishes and manages subscriber sessions. When a session is active, BNG aggregates traffic from various subscriber sessions from an access network, and routes it to the network of the service provider. BNG is deployed by the service provider and is present at the first aggregation point in the network, such as the edge router. An edge router, like the Cisco ASR 9000 Series Router, needs to be configured to act as the BNG.

DSLAM equipment collects the data from its many modems ports & aggregate their voice & data traffic into one complex composite "Signal" via multiplexing. First check for Redundancy of Power Supply / control cards for all the ports. Connect the DSLAM with power supply and log-in using admin through the C-DOT portal. Telnet using command Telnet <ip_address_of IPDSLAM>. Give username and password. Ping PC to IP-DSLAM IP [9]. It should be possible to log in and log out in IPDSLAM. Check date and time setting. Once the controller card is up, the configuration should be there. See the details using commands. Connect ADSL modem at ADSL port. Check for ADSL ports by activating / de-activating one port at a time. After the activation/deactivation of ports done, the simultaneous use of data and phone is working in IP- DSLAM. Now we will generate VDSL, which will be multiplexed with ADSL through DSLAM. This allows us to get more bandwidth and more speed through VDSL on the existing ADSL line going to the customers. We gave the name for this methodology is nxDSL. Log-out from the portal.

Fig-5: Block diagram of proposed DSLAM methodology

The results have been obtained using the real-world environment of C-DOT in the BSNL Exchange laboratory. The following sections are devoted to the process, and its description. The framework will include results comparing the measurement environment, process, and performance of direct propagation with the proposed protocol. For this purpose, we have also used MIS for comparing. Multi service DSLAMs have the capacity of supporting several DSL, so that it is also known as the nxDSL technologies. Multi service DSLAMs allows ISPs or carriers to address the different broadband needs of their customers. Guo-Ming Sung et al. [5] ADSL, with transmission rates varying from 128 Kilobits per second (Kbps) up to 8Megabits per second (Mbps) and operating on reaches up to 12 Kilo feet (Kft) from the central office, was ideally suited for this application. Using a multicarrier modulation technique, known as Discrete Multitone (DMT) modulation that data rates in excess of 6Mbps, equivalent to 4 T1-rate signals of 1.544Mbps [5]. The maximum throughput (speed) for nxDSL is 3 Gb/s download and 0.8Gb/s upload, though it is rare to measure these figures outside of lab conditions. The method of data transmission for nxDSL is PTM (Packet Transfer Mode) with a bandwidth overhead of approximately 5%. DSLAMs optimize high-speed transmission by terminating local subscriber loops and transferring traffic into a high-capacity uplink. In other words, connecting a series of modems to a DSLAM allows a higher-quality link such as fibre to take over to connect customers to the Internet.

